

1 **Gasdermin activation during lineage specification in the human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here gasdermin
9 activation during lineage specification in the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Chi, Z., Chen, S., Yang, D., Cui, W., Lu, Y., Wang, Z., Li, M., Yu, W., Zhang, J., Jiang, Y. and Sun,
12 R., 2024. Gasdermin D-mediated metabolic crosstalk promotes tissue repair. *Nature*, 634(8036),
13 pp.1168-1177.
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